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D3.5: Software Tool for Extracting Relations Between Musical Patterns (V1.0)

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Project Information

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.5 is titled: *Software Tool for Extracting Relations Between Musical Patterns*. It is due month 30, and linked to Task 1 of WP3: *Pattern Extraction*; to Task 2: *Pattern recognition and definition in monodic and polyphonic music* and to Task 3: *Network of musical patterns*. The lead beneficiary is NUIG. This deliverable is also linked with the report deliverable D3.4 *Analysis of found musical patterns to identify their relationships*.

In this document, we briefly outline the collection of software tools delivered as part of D3.5. Each software component is open-source (in Polifonia GitHub) with an associated Zenodo release. The document will include a FAIR statement also.

The collection of software tools is as follows:

Folk N -gram aNalysis (FoNN tools) (NUIG) A set of tools for extracting melodic patterns from folk tunes. Demonstrated on MTC-ANN and *The Session* datasets. Also dissimilarity methods which use these patterns. Dissimilarity methods rely on pattern relationships such as pattern similarity.

Pattern Knowledge Graph (NUIG) Processing the outputs of FoNN tools to produce a knowledge graph; the resulting knowledge graph itself, using MTC-ANN and an annotated subset of *The Session* datasets; and demonstrations in a SPARQL endpoint and MELODY data stories. The KG allows queries for pattern relationships.

Motif Extraction by Local Alignment (CNAM and NUIG) A novel approach to extracting motifs from polyphonic music by taking advantage of relationships among common subsequences across voices when aligned.

Generating Weighted Pitch Context Vectors (KNAW) An approach to music analysis based on representing the *context* (surrounding notes) of a *focus note* as pitch vectors.

Harmory (UNIBO and KCL) Harmory is an approach to harmonic analysis, and a subsequent knowledge graph. It projects chord progressions into a numerical space; segments them into meaningful harmonic structures; and by comparing sequences to each other, it reveals common and recurring harmonic patterns.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
V0.1	25/05/2023	Outline released	James McDermott (NUIG)
V0.2	09/06/2023	Full draft for review	James McDermott (NUIG), Abdul Shahid (NUIG), Danny Diamond (NUIG), Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW), Eoin Kearns (KNAW), Tiange Zhu (CNAM), Raphaël Fournier S'niehotta (CNAM), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO)
V0.3	20/06/2023	Addressing review comments	James McDermott (NUIG), Abdul Shahid (NUIG), Danny Diamond (NUIG), Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW), Eoin Kearns (KNAW), Tiange Zhu (CNAM), Raphaël Fournier S'niehotta (CNAM), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO)
V1.0	30/06/2023	Submission to EU	UNIBO

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1 Folk N-gram aNalysis

ID	https://zenodo.org/record/8047769
Type	Software
Title	FoNN - Folk N-gram aNalysis
Credits	Danny Diamond (NUIG), and James McDermott (NUIG), and Abdul Shahid (NUIG), and Mathieu d'Aquin (NUIG)
Description	Software for mining patterns in musical corpora
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis
Documentation	README.md
Release	v1.0
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	similarity_search_demo.ipynb
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4

1.1 Overview

Folk N -gram aNalysis (FoNN) is a collection of software for extracting patterns from folk tunes. It has been described in detail in previous deliverables D3.3 and D3.4.

The current version is substantially updated with new methods of analysing similarity between melodies.

FoNN addresses the deliverable requirement of *pattern relationships* because a fundamental concept in the updated version of FoNN is the use of approximate pattern matching. That is, when a pattern is found to be important in one tune, related tunes are found on the basis of not only the exact pattern but also related patterns. This pattern relationship is expressed as a threshold on edit distance, specifically *Levenshtein distance* [1].

FoNN contains a music data processing pipeline and three music similarity tools, all of which are focused on detection of similar and frequent patterns within musical feature sequence data extracted from a corpus of music documents in symbolic representation. The workflow overview is illustrated in Figure 1.1.

Our current research uses FoNN tools in a tune family detection task. Tune families are clusters of related melodies commonly found within (and across) folk corpora and folk traditions [2, 3]. Their detection has been the subject of much work, in both computational [3, 4] and traditional musicology [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]; this work overlaps greatly with the core Music Information Retrieval (MIR) task of cover-song detection. FoNN similarity metrics have

Figure 1.1: FoNN workflow

been found to detect tune family members with a high degree of accuracy when tested on a ground-truth annotated corpus of Irish traditional music, as measured via mean Average Precision (mAP)[10].

1.2 Exploitability

The FoNN toolkit contributes to overall Polifonia goals by providing tools to explore relationships between musical patterns. Via FoNN, a user can identify important patterns in tunes, or across a corpus, and identify relationships among tunes in a corpus due to similarity in their local patterns. FoNN has been created by University of Galway (NUIG) but is available on GitHub to all Polifonia partners and to external users[11].

The FoNN tools are available for re-use via Jupyter Notebooks provided on GitHub and documented in the project README file. External users can run these notebooks to extract features and patterns from a symbolic music corpus, run FoNN's similarity tools, and also generate the input data required for creation of a Pattern Knowledge Graph, as discussed in Chapter 2.

The sample datasets provided with FoNN are the Meertens Tune Collection Annotated Corpus (MTC-ANN)[12] and The Session [13], which allow users to explore patterns and similarity in Dutch and Irish folk music. Work on the Meertens collection has been facilitated by Polifonia colleagues in KNAW.

Ultimately, FoNN will function as a component in a web-accessible musicological tool, generating input data which can be presented via a Knowledge Graph, which in turn can be explored and queried via an online user-interface. Knowledge Graphs created from FoNN data are discussed further in Chapter 2, and work on the user-interface is currently underway, via a co-design consultancy process involving a range of domain expert musicologists.

1.3 Future work

An immediate aim is the application of FoNN's similarity tools to a large-scale cross-corpus experiment to explore pattern-based similarity between tunes from multiple European folk traditions. Input data will be sourced from Polifonia partner institutions such as the NEUMA corpus (CNAM) and the Meertens Tune Collection (KNAW), as well as from freely-available online sources such as The Session and the Essen Folksong Collection.

Future research on tune families in European folk corpora will involve development of an additional embedding-based similarity method informed by [14, 15]. This resource will be added to the FoNN tool once development and testing is complete.

A first publication of work using the FoNN toolkit has been drafted for planned publication by end 2023 [10]. Further publications are planned on both the cross-corpus experiment and additional similarity method mentioned above.

The ground-truth annotation created for The Session corpus in the course of our research will also be added to the FoNN toolkit online and documented.

Driven by the outcomes of the user-interface co-design process mentioned above in Section 1.2, collaborative work will continue to evolve and improve the pipeline linking FoNN outputs with the input requirements of the Pattern Knowledge Graph component.

2 Pattern Knowledge graphs

ID	https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph
Type	Knowledge Graph and software for creating Knowledge Graph
Title	Pattern Knowledge Graphs (MTC-ANN and The Session (annotated subset))
Credits	Abdul Shahid (NUIG) and Danny Diamond (NUIG) and James McDermott (NUIG)
Description	Knowledge graphs representing patterns in folk music repositories
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph/
Documentation	readme.md
Release	https://zenodo.org/deposit/8034504
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/fonn/sparql
	http://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/fonn/tune_families_in_the_session_and_mtcann
	http://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/fonn/statistics_on_the_session_annotated_subset_and_meertens_tune_collections_mtcann_pattern_kg
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4

This component includes a software pipeline for transforming music pattern data to a pattern knowledge graph, and also includes the resulting knowledge graph (KG) itself. Ontologies and KGs are used throughout Polifonia, and thus this work feeds into a larger goal of creating a large inter-linked collection of musical heritage data.

The software pipeline we have developed is derived from the Smashub pipeline described by [16, 17] (see Section 5), and takes advantage of the *JAMS* standard for musical annotations [18] and the *SPARQL Anything* tool described by [19].

The inputs to the pipeline are:

- pattern data representing the n -gram patterns found in some corpus of folk tunes, as previously output by Fonn tools (https://github.com/polifonia-project/folk_ngram_analysis);
- metadata, including tune family information.

The pattern data includes the following fields (with types as shown, and examples):

Property	Example	Explanation
identifiers	NLB072355_01	An identifier string for this tune
feature	diatonic scale degree	A string indicating that the pitch values in our pattern will be diatonic scale degree values
level	(duration-weighted) note	A string indicating that we are capturing the pitch on a regular time grid
n_vals	(4, 5, 6)	A tuple of integers indicating the values of n for the n -grams
duration	48	An integer indicating the length of the tune in beats
pattern_locations	{(4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5): [0], (4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 4): [1], (4, 5, 5, 5, 4, 3): [2], (5, 5, 5, 4, 3, 3): [3], etc.}	A dictionary mapping each pattern to locations, where a pattern is a tuple of integers and locations is a list of integers. This example shows that pattern (4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5) occurs at location 0 and at no other location, and so on.
data	[4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, etc.]	A list of integers giving the pitches of the entire tune

The pipeline consists of:

- A Python script (pickle2jams.py) for processing the inputs to produce JAMS files;
- A Python script (jams2rdf.py) which takes JAMS files as inputs and calls SPARQL-Anything with a SPARQL query to produce the knowledge graph as RDF files (ttl format).

Although our methods are generic, we describe their application to two datasets:

- The Session is a large (40,000 tunes) corpus of Irish traditional music, crowd-sourced. We have annotated a small subset with tune family information (315 tunes in 10 tune families). This subset is processed to give a knowledge graph. <https://thesession.org/>
- MTC-ANN is a corpus of Dutch folk music, already annotated with tune family information. <https://www.liederenbank.nl/mtc/>

The resulting KG is uploaded to a Blazegraph instance¹. The KG can be accessed through the Polifonia server², with "data stories" also available as demonstrations via Polifonia MELODY³.

The Pattern Ontology used for our KG is an extension of the existing JAMS ontology, related to the Musical Annotation Pattern (MAP) proposed by [?] as part of Polifonia research. The purpose of the MAP is to model different types of musical annotation such as chords, structure, and patterns. The MAP is based on the JAMS annotation standard [20]. Briefly, JAMS

¹<https://blazegraph.com/>

²<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/fonn/sparql>

³E.g. http://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/fonn/statistics_on_the_session_annotated_subset_and_meertens_tune_collections_mtcann_pattern_kg

is a standard format for musical annotations. It was originally intended for annotations of audio recordings, but can be used for annotations of score data also. JAMS defines a JSON schema in which annotations can be stored, with fields such as `artist` and `title`, and a *list of annotations*, where each annotation includes a `time`, `duration`, and `value`. Such a structure can store, for example, the chord sequence for a song by storing each chord's name as the `value`, together with the start time and duration of that chord observation.

JAMS offers a predefined schema for storing musical patterns⁴. However, this "JKU pattern" includes only a pattern ID field, and does not include pattern contents. Therefore, we need to create a JAMS extension. JAMS offers the possibility to create custom local schemas to store user-defined data. So, a local schema was designed to store JAMS annotations of FoNN-derived patterns, including pattern contents and other information.

We use classes such as `jams:Pattern` and `jams:ScorePatternOccurrence`. Multiple tunes may contain `jams:ScorePatternOccurrences` of the same `jams:Patterns`, and this allows live SPARQL queries in the KG to link from one tune to another.

The Pattern KG addresses the requirement of *pattern relationships* because it allows queries for pattern subsumption. An example is the following. Since a pattern is represented as a string such as `5_2_5_2`, we can discover other patterns which contain this pattern using a regex filter. The query finds such matches and places them in `?pattern`, and finds the tune name and ID for all such matches.

```

SELECT  (concat(?tuneId, "-", ?tuneName) as ?TuneInfo) ?pattern
{
  VALUES ?givenPattern {'5_2_5_2'}
  ?observation jams:ofPattern ?pattern.
  FILTER regex(str(?pattern), ?givenPattern) .
  ?tuneFile jams:includesObservation ?observation.
  ?tuneFile jams:isJAMSAnnotationOf ?musicalComposition.
  ?musicalComposition mc:title ?tuneName.
  ?musicalComposition jams:tuneId ?tuneId.
}
LIMIT 5
    
```

More broadly, SPARQL queries can be used to access our knowledge graphs in flexible ways.

⁴<https://jams.readthedocs.io/en/stable/namespaces/pattern.html#patternjku>

2.1 Exploitability

The Pattern KG is already valuable for data stories, such as the statistics story already mentioned⁵.

In the coming months, the Pattern KG will be used as the backend for a pattern exploration graphical user interface (GUI). This will be delivered as D5.6. A co-design process for this GUI has been followed, involving interview and discussion between WP3 and internal / external musicologists. As a result, we have begun implementation of the GUI. The front-end (in vue.js) will go via a Python Flask app to make SPARQL queries against the Pattern KG, stored in the Blazegraph server mentioned above.

2.2 Future Work

Future work will involve expansion of the dataset. We will import other tune collections such as Neuma and Essen, after they are processed by FoNN tools (see Section. 1). The ontology will also be fully aligned with the Polifonia ontology network (part of deliverables in WP2) for inter-operability and standardisation.

⁵http://projects.dharc.unibo.it/melody/fonn/statistics_on_the_session_annotated_subset_and_meertens_tune_collections_mtcann_pattern_kg

3 Motif Extraction by Local Alignment

ID	https://zenodo.org/record/8020594
Type	Methodology
Title	Motif extraction by local alignment
Credits	Tiange Zhu (CNAM), Danny Diamond (NUIG), James McDermott (NUIG), Raphaël Fournier-S'niehotta (CNAM), Philippe Rigaux (CNAM), and Mathieu d'Aquin (NUIG)
Description	Automatic extraction of motifs from music compositions
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/motif_extraction
Documentation	README.md
Release	v1.0
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	Jupyter Notebook
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4

Motif Extraction by Local Alignment (MELA) is a tool for extracting motif from musical pieces, through a novel methodology which is not specialized to a single genre or musical tradition. An aim is to output a short and focused set of motifs, reducing the requirement for time-intensive human validation of the results.

A musical motif is “*the smallest structural unit possessing thematic identity*” within a piece of music [21]. Motifs are fundamental elements of melody and musical structure, and tend to be highly repetitious [22]. The detection of frequent musical patterns is a long-standing area of work in the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR). The existing pattern discovery research covers both audio and symbolic music, adopting methods generally falling into three broad categories of 1) string or sequence-based [23], 2) geometric pattern discovery, [24], and 3) methods based on machine-learning [25].

We work with interval sequences extracted from digital music scores, and create a segmentation based on pairwise application of the Smith-Waterman local alignment algorithm [26] between all possible voice pairs in a composition. This algorithm has been commonly applied to the task of similarity between pieces of music [4], but not in works on detection of local patterns. The outputs of the segmentation are taken as the input for a string-based motif discovery process. The overall importance of a pattern is measured based on its frequency of occurrence, using a graph that represents the relationship between patterns. The top-ranked patterns are further analyzed and filtered according to their musical (metrical) structure, generating a final set of motifs. In our context, motifs are defined as short

recurring melodic patterns within a piece of music which contain important or characteristic thematic material; it must repeat at least two times throughout a composition, and contain at least three intervals.

Our motif detection algorithm runs on feature sequence data derived from digital scores. Normalised diatonic interval sequences are taken as input, but the tool can also run on other melodic and/or rhythmic feature sequences derived from digital scores, such as diatonic or chromatic pitch class, pitch, or note duration.

The proposed method is proven to generate satisfying results for an intra-opus pattern detection task based on the JKUPDD dataset [27], which contains five annotated, polyphonic Western classical scores. The results presented exhibit a high degree of accuracy, and performance ranks highly compared to other pattern extraction algorithms tested on the JKUPDD dataset [28, 29, 30, 31, 32]. A paper on this work is currently under review [33].

Identified motifs are of importance in use cases which range from thematic analysis of a piece of music or musicological study of the body of work of a composer [34], to characterisation of a musical tradition, genre or period. Apart from being applied to polyphonic melodies, the introduced methodology can also be applied to detect motifs between multiple related monophonic scores, which is potentially of use in the study of tune families or regional styles within folk traditions [22].

Figure 3.1: A framework of motif discovery from polyphonic symbolic music

The whole framework of the proposed method for discovering motifs in polyphonic symbolic music is illustrated in Figure 3.1. Taking a symbolic music score as an input, key-invariant diatonic interval sequences are extracted from each voice, and encoded. Music segmentation is then applied to the encoded sequences via local alignment[26]. A set of patterns are gathered for further discovery, to find a set of potential motifs. The motifs are ranked and filtered based on specific rules and a customized measure of importance, and then analyzed by their music structure information, to select a final list of results.

3.1 Exploitability

The method developed in this work supports related musicological tasks, such as the analysis of characteristic motifs in composition styles, or the classification of music corpora. It also has potential applications in various domains in MIR including music generation. To aid reproducibility, the source code is available on GitHub [35].

3.2 Future Work

We plan to develop the algorithm further via encoding more musicological knowledge, for example following the use of custom musical weights in the local alignment process in [4]. We also intend to apply the algorithm to inter-opus pattern detection in a corpus of monophonic Irish traditional folk tunes on *The Session*[13], which will help gain greater insight into the role of motifs in defining *tune families*[2] (clusters of similar melodies) within the corpus.

4 Generating Weighted Pitch Context Vectors

ID	https://zenodo.org/record/8020644
Type	Software
Title	Pitchcontext
Credits	Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW) and Eoin Kearns (KNAW)
Description	Software for extracting pitch context vectors.
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/pitchcontext
Documentation	README.md
Release	v0.1.9
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Running Instance	
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4

4.1 Overview

One of the essential aspects of Western folk music is that it is orally transmitted among practitioners regardless of formal music training. This is observed in the perception of rules of tonality, such as stable scale tones, modes, and key centres [36]. With this understanding, pitches within a melody can infer different harmonic functions. Most melodies therefore have a harmonic background, or a succession of chords that best fit the melody. Identifying the pitches which are important in the creation of this harmonic background is an integral part of the accompaniment of Western folk music.

Our model proposes a method to summarise the consonance and dissonance of every pitch within a melody. This is achieved by constructing a pitch context vector for each note in the melody, which summarises the preceding and following pitch context of any given note. Using these contexts, it is possible to accomplish a variety of tasks. Melodies can be reduced in complexity through identifying passing tones and dissonant pitches within a local context. These reduced melodies can be used for multiple purposes, such as similarity measures and reduction of ornamentation. Vectors can also be used to determine the implied harmony of a given melody, and to create suitable harmonic progressions at various levels of abstraction.

4.2 Music Representation

We represent the melodies as sequences of feature values, one value per note. In this approach, we use three features as provided by MTCFeatures,¹ namely `pitch40`, `beatstrength`, and `beatinsong`, which gives onset times in units of the beat. The base-40 representation of pitch preserves the pitch spelling [37]. It includes 40 values per octave representing 40 possible pitches starting with C \flat and ending with B \times . We map all pitch values into one octave. We use the encoding as designed by Hewlett with one adaptation: we give the first pitch (C \flat) index 0 instead of index 1, which has a practical advantage when doing the implementation in Python.

We use the `beatstrength` as computed by the `music21` meter model [38, 39]. `Music21` is a Python library for processing symbolic musical scores. We heavily use this library. In the meter model of `music21`, a `beatstrength` is computed for each note, which indicates the metric weight at the moment of onset of the note. The main accent in the measure gets value 1.0, secondary accents get value 0.5, lower metric positions get 0.25, 0.125, etc. As an example, Figure 4.1 shows an example.

Figure 4.1: Example melody with the values for the pitch (base40) and beatstrength per note.

4.3 Weighted Pitch Context Vectors

For a given note, which we indicate as the *focus note*, we consider both a preceding and a following context. These consist of the sequences of notes that are preceding, respectively

¹<https://pvankranenburg.github.io/MTCFeatures/>

Figure 4.2: Example of a Pitch Context Vector. The vector consists of two parts, wpc_{pre} and wpc_{post} , which represent respectively the preceding and the following context. The full Pitch Context Vector is a concatenation of the two parts. Each element in the vector gets a value representing the ‘amount’ of the corresponding pitch that is present in the context.

following the focus note. For both the preceding and the following context we construct a *weighted pitch context vector*. Each of these vectors has 40 elements corresponding to the 40 pitches in base-40 representation. The value of each of the elements represents the ‘amount’ of the corresponding pitch that is present in the context of the focus note. The full context vector is a 80-dimensional vector which is the concatenation of the preceding and following context vectors.

4.3.1 Length of Contexts

Choosing the length of the contexts is not straightforward. It is, in fact, an important parameter in our model. The music21 meter model provides metric information for each note, notably concerning the *beat* and the *beatstrength* of a note (as explained in Section 4.2). This allows us to express the length of the context as a number of beats. This seems a good approach since the beat is a perceptually meaningful unit. Alternatives would be a fixed number of notes or a certain number of measures.

We experimented with different values for the context length, as well as with a variable context length based on the beatstrengths of the surrounding notes. In our resulting implementation the context length is computed as follows. We start with the focus note. For the preceding context, we consider the notes before the focus note in reversed order, starting with the note directly before the focus note, and we keep adding the notes to the context until (and including) we reach a note with beatstrength 1.0. For the following context, the same procedure is followed, except that the first encountered note with beatstrength of 1.0 is not included in the context. In our implementation, it is also a parameter whether to

include the focus note itself into the context or not.

The consequence of this procedure is that for a note on the main accent of the measure (i.e., the first note), the preceding context is the entire previous measure, and the following context is the remainder of the measure of the focus note. In contrast, for notes that are not on the main accent, the preceding context includes all the previous notes in the same measure, while the following context includes the remaining notes in the measure.

4.3.2 Weighting of Context Notes

The contribution of each context note to the value of the corresponding pitch in the pitch context vector is determined by two components: the metric weight (beatstrength) of the context note, and the distance to the focus note.

Intuitively, the duration of a context note has an impact on its importance in the context of the corresponding focus note. Therefore, we do not simply take the beatstrength of the moment of onset of the context note as weighting factor. Instead, we compute a metric grid, which is a succession of evenly spaced moments in score time. The basic unit of the grid, i.e., the distance between two subsequent positions in the grid, is the greatest common divisor of all note durations. Therefore, each note of the melody starts at a position in the grid, and the 'span' of the note mostly includes several grid positions. The metric weighting factor of a context note is the sum of metric weights (beatstrengths) of all positions of the metric grid that are in the 'span' of the note. Thus, the duration of the note, as well as the metric importance of the note are incorporated in the weighting. This approach also accounts for syncopes. During the span of a syncopated note, a grid-position with higher metric weight than the metric weight at the start of the note occurs. This is included in the sum.

Also intuitively, the further a note is away from the focus note, the lower the importance in the context of the focus note. In our model, we use a linearly decreasing windowing function. The metric weighting factor of a given context note is multiplied by the value of this window function at the position of the onset of the context note. The value of the window function during the span of the focus note is 1.0, and is linearly decreasing towards the end of the context. The value at the end of the context is a parameter in our model. We set this to a value slightly higher than 0.0 in order to have some influence of the notes that are at the outer boundaries of the contexts.

4.4 Exploitability

The Weighted Pitch Context Vectors allows for the extraction of useful information about the harmonic context of any given monophonic melody. This can support various musicological tasks, such as reducing the complexity of melodies for classification or analysis purposes, as well as to identify composition style and influences.

Through adjusting parameters concerning context length and metric weighting, the model is extremely flexible and readily adapted to other functions. We envisage this model will be used for algorithmic composition and for research purposes. The source code is available to all members of Polifonia and external users on Github.

4.5 Future Work

The model will be used to analyse the implied harmony of folk music, and can serve as a tool for composing and performing music.

The model will be implemented to detect and indicate notes which are ornamental in function in a melody, thereby reducing the complexity of a melody. The model can generate suitable harmonic progressions without training, and therefore can be used in many different genres for algorithmic composition. This may also assist other MIR tasks such as pattern recognition and structure analysis.

The model will be further developed to overcome issues with context lengths in pieces of music with free metre by allowing users to set the context length for each focus note by number of notes, regardless of metric weighting. It will also be possible to choose a defined number of metric beats, regardless of number of notes. The model will allow the option to use Inner Metric Analysis to determine context lengths [40]. Finally, a user-interface is being developed for the model in conjunction with members of Polifonia, which can be queried.

5 The Harmonic Memory

ID	https://zenodo.org/record/8021211
Type	Software
Title	Harmory - The Harmonic Memory
Credits	Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL), and Andrea Poltronieri (UNIBO), and Albert Meroño-Peñuela (KCL), and Valentina Presutti (UNIBO)
Description	Software for creating the Harmonic Memory
Source Code	https://github.com/smashub/harmory
Documentation	README.md
Release	v1.0-dev
Licence	CC BY 4.0 , and CC BY NC SA 4.0 (more details from the README)
Running Instance	KG endpoint
Bibliography	de Berardinis, J., Meroño-Peñuela, A., Poltronieri, A., & Presutti, V. (2023, April). The Harmonic Memory: a Knowledge Graph of harmonic patterns as a trustworthy framework for computational creativity. In Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023 (pp. 3873-3882).
Related Deliverables	<i>(methodology to be documented in forthcoming deliverables)</i>

The Harmonic Memory (Harmory) [17] is a Knowledge Graph of interconnected harmonic patterns aimed to support creative applications in a fully transparent, accountable, and musically plausible way. The creation of Harmory is underpinned by state of the art methods for computational music analysis, which will be detailed in a forthcoming deliverable. The contributions documented here focus on the software we developed to support these tasks:

- **Harmonic segmentation**, to split harmonic sequences at meaningful boundaries;
- **Harmonic similarity**, to find connections between harmonic segments.

5.1 Overview

We leverage the Tonal Pitch Space [41] - a cognitive model of Western tonal harmony to project chord progressions into a numerical space that is both musicologically and perceptually plausible. Then, we use novelty-based methods [42] for structural analysis to segment chord sequences into meaningful harmonic structures. The latter are then compared with each other, across all progressions and via harmonic similarity, to reveal common/recurring harmonic patterns.

A KG is created to semantically establish relationships between patterns, based on: (i) temporal links, connecting two patterns if they are observed consecutively in the same

progression; and (ii) similarity links among highly-similar patterns. By traversing the KG, and moving across patterns via temporal and similarity links, new progressions can be created in a combinational settings; but also, unexpected and surprising relationships can be found among pieces and composers of different genre, style, and historical period. This is also enabled by the scale and diversity of Harmory, which is built from ChoCo [43], the largest existing collection of harmonic annotations¹.

Currently, Harmory contains 26K harmonic segments from 1800 harmonic annotations of chords and keys (approximately 10% of ChoCo, corresponding to all the audio partitions). Out of all segments: 13667 (16%) correspond to the same pattern families, 66175 (53%) are pattern-friendly (they share non-trivial similarities with other segments), whereas 8176 (32%) are inherently unique (they are found in other songs). Statistics on harmonic patterns emerging from the analysis of similarities (a byproduct of the software reported in this deliverable are also available online²).

Harmory is part of the Polifonia Ecosystem through its component annotation³ and the repository provides documentation to reproduce all the steps necessary for its creation. The methodology for harmonic segmentation, similarity, Knowledge Graph creation, as well as the example applications, have been documented and peer-reviewed in [17].

5.2 Reproducibility

5.2.1 Segmentation and similarity

The main entry point to perform harmonic segmentation and similarity is implemented via the `create.py` script, which conveniently provides a command line interface. To find harmonic segments, the software expects chord progressions annotated in JAMS files [20], which are fetched from the ChoCo dataset [43]. Harmonic patterns are then dumped in `joblib` format for each progression, and their original representation (as chord subsequences) is also stored for facilitating retrieval operations. Through the `similarity` option, the `create` script takes the segmented harmonic structures as input and run the similarity search across the whole corpus. Similarities are ranked and filtered based on their strength in such a way as to reduce the search space and the memory requirements of the resulting graph. Detailed instructions on how to perform the aforementioned steps are given in the README (c.f. software table).

5.2.2 Experiments and validation

To validate Harmory, we carried out experiments to test the efficacy of the two central components underpinning its creation: the harmonic similarity method, and the harmonic

¹ChoCo is another output of Polifonia, which is documented in D1.5 and D2.4.

²<https://github.com/smashub/harmory/blob/main/harmory/analysis.ipynb>

³<https://github.com/smashub/harmory/blob/main/assets/header.md>

segmentation. This section provides instructions to reproduce our experiments.

Evaluating our harmonic similarity. Our method for harmonic similarity is compared to other state-of-the-art algorithms on the cover song detection task - a common benchmark for similarity algorithms in the symbolic music domain. It is possible to compare performance in the cover song detection task using the following algorithms:

- Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) – a well-known algorithm for time series alignment;
- Tonal Pitch Step Distance (TPSD) [44] – a state of the art method for harmonic similarity based on the Tonal Pitch Space (TPS) [41];
- SoftDTW [45] – a variant of DTW that allows for non-binary (fuzzy) alignments between time series, by using a soft-constraint; with quadratic time/space complexity;
- Longest Common Subsequence Similarity (LCSS) – a method expressing time series similarity based on their longest common subsequence.

It is also possible to preprocess the chord data using two different variants of the TPS distance:

- *Profile*: the TPS distance is computed between the chord and the local key;
- *Offset*: the TPS distance is computed between the chord and its preceding chord.

Moreover, the timeseries produced using both mode of the TPS distance can be normalised both temporally and in terms of the values contained in the series. Finally, you can test different constraint settings for the cover song detection task for the DTW, SoftDTW and LCSS algorithms, namely the Sakoe Chiba and the Itakura constraints.

Structural coverage of known patterns. To evaluate our harmonic segmentation, we provide software to measure the overlap between the resulting structures with a collection of well-known chordal patterns. This exemplifies the hypothesis that a good segmentation would maximise the “reuse” of harmonic patterns - as building blocks that can be found in other pieces.

The baselines implemented in our software are defined for time series segmentation: fast low-cost unipotent semantic segmentation (FLUSS) [46], and a static uniform split. Segmentations are evaluated by computing the structural coverage of known harmonic patterns (which are stored in `data/known-patterns`). For this, we wrapped all commands in a single script (`segval.sh`).

5.3 Exploitability

This work contributed state of the art methods for harmonic similarity and segmentation. The main strength of our approach lies in the musicological and the perceptual plausibility of the representation used to encode chords, as well as the full explainability of our methods – compared to purely learning-based approaches. Through our codebase, which makes all

methods and experiments available for use, we envisage adoption in computational musicology and music information retrieval. Similarity measures for symbolic music are indeed of interest for several applications, including query by humming, composer identification, influence modelling, and music recommendation; whereas harmonic segmentation has clear parallels with other MIR tasks – such as pattern recognition and music structure analysis.

5.4 Future Work

To improve opportunities for reuse, our plans include the extension of our software with full API support on harmonic similarity and segmentation. This will lead to the the release of a first Python library that, on one hand, will facilitate the use of our methods in our project; and on the other hand, will also streamline the inclusion of additional chordal data in the Harmory KG. Future work will also focus on the development of visualisation methods to facilitate the inspection of harmonic similarities, and their sonification.

6 Compliance to the FAIR principles

In this chapter we describe the approach to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles in respect of the software components of this deliverable.

This deliverable is a software deliverable, containing several components of the Polifonia Ecosystem. While producing this deliverable we observed the 'Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science'.¹

The Netherlands eScience Center and DANS recommend the following five action items for FAIR software²:

Use a publicly accessible repository with version control Done (GitHub)

Add a license Done (CC-BY 4 in most cases, see individual components)

Register your code in a community repository Done (Zenodo releases)

Enable citation of the software Done (bibtex citations in README.md)

Use a software quality checklist Done during deliverable review³.

In accordance with common open-source practice we have developed our software in the open, in GitHub. GitHub provides findability and accessibility and long-term persistence.

A large majority of code is written in Python and/or Jupyter Notebook, using common installation methods (conda, requirements.txt) and common third-party libraries such as: the time-series analysis library with a scikit-learn interface tslearn; the data conversion tool SPARQL Anything; and the common music information retrieval library Music21. This ensures compatibility with many other pieces of software in related fields. It also ensures that authors and researchers face few obstacles in learning from or contributing to our software.

Both input data and output data are stored in standardised, documented, common formats with certainty of long-term accessibility, including csv and the Python pickle format (<https://docs.python.org/3/library/pickle.html>). Thus interoperability and reusability are ensured.

The software has also been archived on Zenodo for long-term persistence of the specific version reported here.

Any extra details on the components' FAIR aspects are below.

¹Described in the Polifonia Data Management Plan, 2nd version.

²<https://fair-software.eu/>

³The checklist is internal, but available to Polifonia members and on request: <https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/polifonia/Shared%20Documents/Deliverables/software-deliverable-checklist.docx?d=w15bea5d87fc34a1a812c8cad237aecbd&csf=1&web=1&e=45XBMC>

FONN - Folk N-gram aNalysis Type: software, with accompanying Documentation. In GitHub and Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license.

Pattern Knowledge Graph Ontology and creation pipeline Type: Software, with accompanying Documentation. In GitHub and Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license.

MTC-ANN Pattern Knowledge Graph, and accompanying SPARQL queries Type: KG. In GitHub and Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license. Alignment with Polifonia Ontology Network is ongoing and will help with interoperability.

The Session (small) Pattern Knowledge Graph Similar to above, but for a small subset of *The Session*. The full version of The Session is 45M statements and is not provided at this time.

Harmory Type: Software, with accompanying Documentation. In GitHub and Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license. This software is at <https://github.com/smashub/harmory>, under the *smashub* organisation rather than the *Polifonia* organisation.

Context Vectors Type: Software, with accompanying Documentation. In GitHub and Zenodo with appropriate metadata and license.

Motif extraction by local alignment Type: Software, with accompanying Documentation. In GitHub with appropriate metadata and license.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable has reported on software tools for identifying and processing patterns, using them to answer research questions, and making them available as linked open data. These patterns are of several types, including melodic, motif-like, and harmonic.

Several strands of research are ongoing and planned for forthcoming deliverables:

- Cross-corpus pattern analysis – already enabled by our methods.
- New types of patterns, including:
 - Polyphonic patterns.
 - Ornamentation patterns.
 - Structural patterns.
- Refinements to pattern similarity methods.
- Further research results involving music similarity and classification (D3.6) based on the existing pattern methods described here.

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